

PROBLEMS OF RURAL SPINSTER – A SOCIOLOGICAL STUDY

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Abstract:

Spinster is a unmarried women and who is no longer young and seems unlikely ever marry. There are so many success story of spinster. But in this study, researcher try to portrait the picture of rural uneducated and unemployment spinster. The board aim of the present study is examined the various problems facing by rural spinster. The study was conducted at Majuli districts of Assam. Among the 20 gaonpanchayat of Majuli, Pakajaraonpanchayat was selected randomly. 20 respondents were selected as sampling through purposive sampling method. The samples were selected as a respondent above the age group of 40 years. The interview cum structure schedule was specially prepared for primary data collection. The observation and case study method are also used for data collection. The study was conducted on both qualitative and quantitative methodology. The spinsters are facing so many problems in everyday life. Through this paper we may find out major problems of spinster which will help to reader, policy maker, government and N.G.O.

Key Words: Spinster, Women, Unemployment, Problem & Rural

Introduction:

Marriage is most important social institutions establish to control and regulate the life of human among all over the world. For, Hindus marriage is a sacrament. The major objectives of Hindu life dharma, Artha, Kama and Muksha can be dissolved through marriage only. According to H.T. Mazumdar (1966-502) marriage is a socially sanction union of male and female for the purpose of establishing (a) household (b) entering in to sex relationship (c) procreation and (d) providing care for the offspring;. India is a country where marriage is compulsion for every adult individual. The unmarried is still considered as social stigma.

The status of unmarried is very negligible in rural Indian scenario. The married women are enjoying more status than unmarried women in the filled of socially sanction festival and ritual activities. There are gender gap between single men and women. In the eye of society the unmarried men enjoying more social status than the unmarried women. Beri, A & Beri, N (2013-856) “Single men are seen as” Bachelors”- independent, having fun, and enjoying life to its fullest before getting “Chained down” by a woman. Single women on the other hand, have long been seen as less than whole if they are not attached, lonely spinster, and cat ladies.”

According to Indian law, the legal marriage age of women is 18 years and 21 years for man. Unmarried and singlehood of an individual is unexpected for every society. According to 2011 census 7.4 of women in the country are unmarried, separated and divorce as widow. Spinster is a socially constructed category of a society. According to Cambridge dictionary, spinster are those women, who is not married, especially a woman who is no longer young and seems unlikely ever to marry”.

Review:

Phillimore, P. (1991) In his study examined the social position of unmarried women in the local village as well as wider society. He mentioned that the unmarried women not only facing problems in her life but also stand as burden of family member. Due to lack of specific social strata of unmarried women, they are enjoying limited status in the society.

Mukhopadhyay, J. (2016) In his study he classified the Indian single women on the basis of divorce, widow and never unmarried women. He mentioned that Indian single women is still far away from emancipation of patriarchal domination. The single women face social and psychological harassment every field of activities. The never unmarried women are sometime considered as a ‘not enticing’ unlucky, loose moral, a rebel in the eye of society.

Budgeon, S. (2016) In her study used the gender hegemony model for understanding how and why choosing to single may lead to problems for women. Due to establish ideology of marriage and family, single women’s identity work resolve contradiction in the gender order and process reinstates heteronormativity.

Dakuah, A. (2015) In his article he mentioned that women are victimized and exploited by the society but unmarried women are double exploitation in the society. The unmarried women harassed by the family member due to economic insecurity and dependence on family member. He cited that status of single women is very negligible because single women can’t full role of wives and mother. The unmarried women are imposed by the society in the participation of some religious and cultural occasion.

Krishnakumari (1987) in her study examines how single woman facing problems in various activities. He mentioned that the single woman facing problems family and work place. They are facing Inner conflict as well as working commitment in the work place.

The major objectives of the present study are-

- To trace the social and economic back ground of the respondents.
- To find out the major problems of spinster.
- To identify their future prospects of spinster.

Study Area:

The study was conducted at Majuli district of Assam. The island is form by the Brahmaputra river in the south and kherkhutiasuti an ana branch of Brahmaputra joined by Subansiririver in the North. According to 2014, the total land area of Majuli is 352km (approx.) . As per census 2011, Majuli had population of 167,304 of which 85,325 were male and 81,978 were female. Among the 20 gaon panchayat of Majulipakajaraon panchayat was selected as a field of study. Pakajaraonpanchayat is located remote area and situated medium part of Majuli.

Methodology:

The study involved conducting interview with spinster in Majuli using interview guide. Structure and semi structure schedule was specially prepared for collecting required information, fact, data and opinion. Case study method was also adopted for intensive and depth study. The researcher also made site visit in order to observe circumstance and environment of the spinster family. The required secondary date were collected through book, Journal, article and government report. 20 sample were selected through purposive sampling methodas a respondents from various village. In the time of primary data collection the researcher was strictly maintain the research ethics.

Social Background of the Respondents:

Due to cultural variation and changing structure of the society it is very important to study background of respondents. The social and economic background of an individual reflect cultural norms, value, tradition, beliefs, custom and practices of a particular society. As a peculiar part of research we may arrived at future notion of research through information of social background of respondents. In this chapter background of respondents includes age, education, family status, occupation, religion and caste.

Age is very important component for understanding of social background of an individual. Although individual thought, intelligent, idea, rational mindsets are not pre-determined by nature but through the age, individual learn skill of expression rational thinking, comprehensive mindset and capable of taking right decision in right time through experience. Among the 20 respondents of spinster,60% respondents were counterparts from age group of 40-45. 30% respondents from age group of 45-50 and only 10% respondents represent from the age group of 50-55%. The educational qualification was very negligible among the spinster.Only 20% of respondents have finished H.S.L.C. exam 50% of respondent left school at high school level and another 30% of them finished primary school. Due to rural area in nature 70% of respondent counterparts from joint family and 30% of respondents lives in the nuclear family. Most of the spinsters are working in the household activities, only 10% of them are engaged with non-government activities. Occupation is another important component to know about life style of a individual. Among the 20 respondents 90% of respondent working at household activities in the family and only 10% of them engaged in some other activity. None of them was well established. They are just living by hook or cook condition. All the respondents werebelong from Hindu religion.

Problems of Spinster:

The problems of spinster is different from society to society according to income and educational status of a spinster. In this chapter researcher try to portrait a picture of rural unemployment spinster. Spinster is a social problem. No one willing to become a spinster. There are so many social and economic condition associated with being women unmarried. Thought the primary data collection it was found that 50% of women abstained from marriage due lost their parents at childhood and support family member. 40% of them being unmarried due to unable choice perfect partner and another 10% of them unmarried because of their physical disabilities. The spinster of rural area spent their life in very negligible condition. The major problem facing by the rural spinsters are mention bellow:

Economic Problem:

Economic problems in the major problems of spinster. The spinster have neither higher education nor technical education to become economically and mentally sound. Most of the spinster depends on income of family member. Some of them earn money thought weaving, animal husbandry and farm activities. According to Hindu patriarchal tradition the women are not able to enjoying father land or property after his death. After the death of her parents, the spinster harassed by the family member. The member of the family thinks him as a burden. The spinster are engaged in various activities like weaving, child care, animal husbandry and farm activities but the monopoly of their work go to the family member. Due to poor economic condition the spinster are feeling insecurity in the old age.

Social Problem:

Social problem is the another problems for spinster. Due to single in nature, the social contact among the people is decreased during her life span. Marriage perpetuates kinship group. Due to less number of kin, they are not able to maintain the cohesiveness in the society and thus they are deprived from the society. In rural

Indianscenario the unmarried single man has more demand than unmarried women in the eye of society. Life without marriage is considered as a social stigma among the unmarried women.

Marriage is the ultimate goal according to Hindu religious tradition. Women can performed religious activities with her partner through marriage. Spinster are considered as a impure to performed religious activities. In some ritual and social activities the participation of spinster is imposed by the sriety. Sometime the sprinters are blame as a inauspicious, prostitute in the society.

Psychological Problem:

Psychological problem is the another problems for the spinster. The spinster are felling insecurity and loneliness due to their social position in the society. Due to less participation in the social activities, they became loneliness in day to day life. They became socially and individually deprived from the society. The spinster can't share her emotion, fillings due to lack of intimate person. The spinster also psychologically felling insecure due to low status in comparison to married women.

Problems at Family:

The spinster are not secure at family also. After the death of her parents the spinster spent in negligible condition. Although the spinster is elder among the all family member but she cant's take any important decision in the family. She became the burden of the family. Due to poor economic condition the spinster felling insecure for the old age.

Future Prospect for Spinster:

Spinster is also a part of our society. For over all development of the society we must give importance on every section of the society. No one willingly become spinster. As a social problem everyone has responsibility to take care of spinster. For future prospect of the spinster government and society should need to take some initiative. The essential initiative are discuss bellow-

- The spinster are depressing due to so many condition. So the government and non-government organization should need to provide motivational workshop or speech among the spin ster.
- The rural unemployment spinster facing so many economic problems during the middleage. So, government should need to provide special training to all the unemployment single women for self sustain.
- Most of the spinster felling insecurity for future condition of old age. The government and non-government organization should need to establish some institution like women club, old age special home for betterments of spinster.
- Government should need to provide special scheme for physically disabilities spinster.
- The people of society must be need to create sympathetic environment and support mentally as well provides equal right to them in every aspect.

Conclusion:

The study was undertaken in Majuli with prime objective of find out various problems facing by the rural spinster. Most of spinster was uneducated and unemployment. The life style of spinster was very negligible. The study reveals that the spinster of Majuli facing so many problems like economic social, psychological and accommodation. The spinster are feeling loneliness in terms of emotion, security, mental support and so, on. As a social problem every citizen have responsibility to create conducive environment for future prospect of the spinster.

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